

- Data subject rights driven studies
 - Hard to conduct
 - Scalability limitation
- Is Citizen science the answer?
 - Success story in Astronomy, CS, Ecology, etc. - Galaxy Zoo
 - Education outreach
 - Cost effective
- How to motivate participation?
 - Delegation – a more knowledgeable person takes the lead in the exercise of data subject rights.

Applying Citizen Science to Improve the Scalability of Data
Subject Rights Driven Research Studies
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